

Journalism Science Alliance

**CALL FOR
APPLICANTS - I**

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project name	Journalism and Science Alliance
Project acronym	JSA
Grant number	101180216
Project coordinator	António Granado, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa
Project duration	01/04/2025 - 31/03/2027

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable identification	D2.1 Call for applicants - I		
Due date	30/06/2025		
Actual submission date	24/06/2025		
Contributing partners	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA, EUROPEAN JOURNALISM CENTRE		
Deliverable type	R	Document, report	X
	DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
	DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos etc.	
	OTHER		
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
CALL FOR APPLICATIONS	5
ELIGIBILITY TO APPLY	5
MENTORSHIP AND TRAINING	6
NETWORKING	6
HOW TO APPLY	7
SELECTION PROCESS AND TIMELINE	7
PAYMENTS AND REPORTING	8
QUESTIONS AND CONTACT	8
APPLICATION QUESTIONS (FOR LEAD APPLICANTS)	10
APPLICATION DETAILS	10
ABOUT YOUR PROJECT	11
TERMS AND CONDITIONS	12
FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS	14

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 – TIMELINE OF CALL FOR APPLICANTS.....	7
--	---

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The first part of this document presents the Call for Applicants concerning the first call of Journalism Science Alliance (JSA) grants, released on 2 June. The Call for Applications outlines details of the JSA, the eligibility criteria, conditions of the grant, and selection criteria, and the proposed timeline for grantees.

The second part of the document provides the application questions for lead-applicants, which intend to help the applicants to prepare their application information properly before starting their submission. This second part contains all the queries that applicants are asked in the submission form and helps them to prepare their answers in advance.

The third part exhibits the frequently asked questions about JSA, notably details about the programme, the grants, the application procedure, the eligibility and selection criteria and the contacts in case of doubts.

All the information presented in this deliverable report is available at <https://ejc.net/funding/journalism-science-alliance> and also accessible via <https://journalismsciencealliance.eu/>.

CALL FOR APPLICATIONS

Open date: 2 June 2025

Closing date: 4 August 2025 (17:00 CEST)

The Journalism Science Alliance (JSA) is a programme co-funded by the EU's Creative Europe Programme. JSA delivers grant funding, training, mentoring and networking to drive the production of local, regional, and transnational investigative journalism backed by science, and enhance cross-sectoral collaboration between journalism and research institutions. Supported by training and mentorship provided by JSA, journalists and scientists will work together to uncover new topics of public interest that will reach and engage (new) audiences for investigative journalism, while serving public interest across Europe.

The JSA is managed by a consortium led by [NOVA University Lisbon](#) (NOVA), in partnership with the [European Journalism Centre](#) (EJC).

ELIGIBILITY TO APPLY

The grants will be open to:

- Collaborations involving at least one media outlet and one research/academic organisation working on an investigation on a topic of public interest, such as climate change, healthcare, emerging technologies, local governance, etc. The list of examples is not exhaustive.
- Organisations need to be based in one or more countries that have signed up to the full [cross-sectoral strand](#) of the European Union's [Creative Europe Programme](#), which provides core funding for the JSA.
Eligible countries include all 27 EU member states and the following non-EU countries: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Georgia, Iceland, Liechtenstein, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia and Ukraine.
- The lead applicant is always a media outlet. The application should be submitted by a journalist associated with that media outlet who will act as the team lead. This can also be a freelancer, as long as they are supported by a media outlet.
- Individual journalists and/or scientists can be part of the applying teams as long as there are at least two organisations already involved in the application (1 media and 1 research organisation), but they cannot be lead applicant.

- Media, journalists, scientists, and/or research organisations from outside of the Creative Europe participating countries will be able to be part of the applying teams, as long as these already include one media and one research entity that satisfy the eligibility criteria.

Grant funding may be used to cover any costs necessary for the development, completion and publication of the research and production of journalistic content, including salary and human resource costs, research-related costs, translation and travel costs. The only exception applies to equipment (hardware) costs, which are not eligible.

There will be two Calls for Applications during the 2025/26 funding round.

We are now launching the **first Call** within this programme. We are allocating approximately one million euro for supporting the first round of journalistic projects. Teams can apply for grants of 10,000 euro, 20,000 euro or 50,000 euro, depending on the scope of their project, the complexity of the proposed investigations, the number of partners involved, the nature of the associated tasks and the tentative timeline.

MENTORSHIP AND TRAINING

Each awarded team will work with one or more carefully selected mentors according to how their needs evolve as they proceed with their projects. Teams can decide which team members will communicate with the mentor(s) throughout the programme. Mentors will commit to being available on particular days for calls, emails, feedback sessions etc. throughout the course of the projects. The mentors will have expertise in various aspects of journalism (for example, data journalism, pitching, open-source intelligence, best practices in science reporting and so on).

In addition to the mentoring programme, the EJC will organise online expert calls (“Ask Me Anything” sessions) with specialists to allow grantees of the scheme to gain knowledge and improve their skills in fields relevant to investigative journalism.

NETWORKING

In addition to the in-person networking opportunities for all JSA grantees provided by the programme, EJC will organise a half-day online event bringing together each awarded cohort of JSA Scheme at the start of their projects.

These online events will be in a format that encourages active participation from grantees, allowing them to align their expectations and fostering knowledge sharing and collaboration.

HOW TO APPLY

- Create an [EJC.net account](#) or log in if you have an existing account.
- Make sure you have thoroughly read and understood the [Call for Applications](#) document.
- Download the [Application Questions](#) document before starting your application. This document contains all the questions you'll be asked and helps you prepare your answers in advance.
- Click the "Apply button" on the [funding page](#) to start your application.

Applications must be received by 17:00 CEST on Monday 4 August 2025.

Applicants can save the application form and return to it until they have completed it and are ready to submit. Once the application is submitted, it can no longer be edited. Only applications received via the EJC platform by the stated date and time will be considered. You will receive an email confirmation of your submission.

Applications must be completed in English but supporting documents that are provided by weblink or upload can be in applicants' native language.

SELECTION PROCESS AND TIMELINE

Table 1 – TIMELINE OF CALL FOR APPLICANTS

Dates (subject to change)	Activity
2 June 2025	Call for Applications opens
16 June 2025 (11.00 CEST)	AMA session I
7 July 2025 (11.00 CEST)	AMA session II
4 August 2025 (17:00 CEST)	Call for Applications closes
September 2025 (date tbd)	Judging of applications, shortlisting and due diligence checks
October 2025 (date tbd)	Notification winners, signing of agreements, initial grant payments
November 2025–June 2026	Grant period
28 February 2026	Interim report grantees
15 July 2026	Final report grantees

The selection of successful applications is done by an independent jury made up of distinguished journalists and scientists.

Successful applicants will be notified about the outcome of their application as soon as the independent jury makes its decision. Given the expected high volume of applications, the Consortium reserves the right to not provide individual feedback to unsuccessful applicants.

Grants are awarded for a period of 8 months. All funded projects must be finalised no later than the date specified in the grant agreement.

PAYMENTS AND REPORTING

For teams selected for grant funding, the payment of grants will be made in three instalments:

- 50% of the grant amount will be paid upon signing of the grant agreement by the awarded project team and upon counter-signing by the EJC.
- 30% following the submission of a mid-term narrative report and completion of agreed milestones.
- The remaining 20% will be paid following the submission of a final report by the project team, demonstrating the fulfilment of the grant requirements.

QUESTIONS AND CONTACT

If you have a query that isn't answered in this document, please refer to the [FAQs](#). The [Application Questions](#) document can be used to prepare your application. Please note: This document is designed to preview the application questions and prepare accordingly. This is not the actual application form. Please Create an [EJC.net account](#) to apply.

You can also join the AMA ('Ask Me Anything') sessions via Zoom. There will be two sessions for the first Call on:

- Monday 16 June 2025 at 11.00 CEST
To attend, please follow the Zoom link [here](#) or [add it to your calendar](#).
- Monday 7 July 2025 at 11.00 CEST
To attend, please follow the Zoom link [here](#) or [add it to your calendar](#).

Our FAQ section provides answers to many specific questions about the grant. For further questions, applicants should contact the European Journalism Centre at jsagrants@ejc.net.

APPLICATION QUESTIONS (FOR LEAD APPLICANTS)

APPLICATION DETAILS

LEAD APPLICANT (MEDIA OUTLET)

Project name. Please write the title of your project here.

- Your organisation's registered address. (If your organisation has several offices, provide the address for the office where you are based)
 - Your organisation's website address
 - Your organisation's social media profiles
 - Your organisation's entity number / registration details (e.g. Chamber of Commerce)

 - First and last name of the team lead (journalist)
(You are deemed the 'Team Lead' as you are completing and submitting this application individually or on behalf of the whole applying team)
 - Job title of the team lead
 - Email address
 - Work number of the team lead (include the country code)
 - Country of residence of the team lead
- ⇒ Please confirm that your organisation has a bank account that accepts international payments (from the Netherlands)

CO-LEAD APPLICANT (RESEARCH INSTITUTION)

- Your research Institution's full legal name
- Your organisation's registered address. (If your organisation has several offices, provide the address for the office where you are based)
- Your organisation's website address
- Your organisation's social media profiles
- Your organisation's entity number / registration details (e.g. Chamber of Commerce)

- First and last name of the co-lead (scientist)
(The co-lead scientist has the overall responsibility for the project on behalf of the research organisation)
- Job title of the co-lead

- Email address
- Work number of the co-lead (include the country code)
- Country of residence of co-lead

TEAM DESCRIPTION

Please provide an overview of the team of journalists and scientists involved in this proposal, including a brief explanation of why they are qualified to successfully carry out the project. (max. 1500 characters).

Please upload CVs of the team members (2 pages max. per CV).

Please select the countries where all team members of the applying team are based (check all that apply), including countries that do not participate in the EU's Creative Europe Programme.

ABOUT YOUR PROJECT

PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Briefly tell us what you plan to investigate (max. 5000 characters):

1. What public interest issue(s) it will focus on;
2. What new information your proposed investigation will reveal;
3. What scientific area(s) will be involved. How the scientific expertise contributes to the story.

Project relevance. Please indicate why this story would be a contribution to the public interest in the countries involved and/or in the EU more broadly. (max. 2500 characters)

Methodology. How do you intend to pursue your objective? Type of sources? Tools? Techniques? (max. 2500 characters)

Collaboration plan. Please explain how the research organisation will be involved and how scientific research will benefit the investigation. (2500 characters)

Dissemination plan. Please provide the activity timeline for your investigation and explain how and when you plan to broadcast, publish or share your findings. (max. 2500 characters)

One story or more. Please provide an estimate of how many stories you plan to publish within this project.

Impact. Please describe expected results and impact of your story/ies. (max. 2500 characters)

RISK ASSESSMENT

Please describe the ethical considerations associated with the completion of your project and how you plan to mitigate against these considerations. (max. 2000 characters).

Please list the risks associated with the completion of your project and how you plan to mitigate against these risks.

BUDGET

Select your tier based on the complexity of the proposed investigations, the number of partners involved, the nature of the associated tasks and the tentative timeline

- Tier 1: € 10,000
- Tier 2: € 20,000
- Tier 3: € 50,000

Please download the [budget template](#), fill it out and then upload it. The budget must be in euro.

Budget justification. Please briefly provide any additional information needed to justify the costs you have included in your budget. (max. 1500 characters)

(The budget should contain sufficient detail so as to allow the jury to assess the feasibility and relevance of your proposed costs. For eligible and ineligible project costs, refer to the [Call for Applications](#) document.)

How will you ensure gender balance, inclusion and diversity in your project and in the way of managing the tasks/activities? (max. 1500 characters)

TERMS AND CONDITIONS

- You have read, in full, and understand the Call for Applications document, which outlines details of the Journalism Science Alliance, the eligibility criteria, conditions of the grant, and selection criteria, and the proposed timeline for grantees.
- You agree that the information provided in this application is correct at the time of completion, and that the European Journalism Centre can use the information to shortlist and select successful applications for grant funding. You understand that your data will be processed in accordance with the [EJC Privacy Policy](#).
- You agree that the information provided in this application can be published by the EJC, along with other intelligence and data generated by the Alliance, for the purposes of informing the end-of-Programme evaluation, and sharing learnings with other

practitioners, the wider industry and the Programme Partners. All business-sensitive information provided will be anonymised before being published publicly.

- You understand that your data may also be shared with our programme partner, NOVA, for the purposes of jointly managing this application. Processing will happen according to the [NOVA Privacy Policy](#).

ALMOST THERE...

Your submission is currently not submitted.

Once you click finish below, your application will be closed and final. You will no longer be able to come back and make changes to the application.

Ready to submit your application?

Here's a final checklist to make sure you've covered everything:

- Are your contact details correct?
- Is your research and publication plan as concrete as possible?
- Does the budget tier you selected correspond to the estimated efforts?
- Have you attached all relevant documents?

FREQUENTLY ASKED QUESTIONS

WHAT IS JSA AND WHAT DOES IT DO?

The Journalism & Science Alliance (JSA) is a programme co-funded by Creative Europe, that delivers grant funding, training, mentoring and networking to drive the production of local, regional, and transnational investigative journalism backed by science, and enhance cross-sectoral collaboration between journalism and research institutions. Supported by training and mentorship provided by JSA, journalists and scientists will work together to uncover new topics of public interest that will reach and engage (new) audiences for investigative journalism, while serving public interest across Europe.

WHO MANAGES THE JSA PROGRAMME?

The JSA Fund is managed by a consortium led by NOVA University Lisbon, in partnership with the European Journalism Centre (EJC).

WHAT ARE THE JSA GRANTS?

JSA grants aim to forge new alliances between media and academia or research institutions, ramp up pertinent skills and operations, and deliver in-depth investigative reporting on topics of public interest, ranging from climate change and healthcare to emerging technologies and local governance. The programme will allocate a total of €2 million in grants over a 24-month project lifecycle.

JSA will award three types of grants:

- € 10 000
- € 20 000
- € 50 000

Applying teams choose which tier to apply and justify their choice in the application regarding the complexity of the proposed investigations, the number of partners involved, the nature of the associated tasks and the tentative timeline. Participating partners must agree on the distribution of funds and the procedures to be followed at the stage of the preparation of their application.

How many calls (rounds of funding) are planned?

Two calls will be held in 2025/26, opening on the following dates:

- First call: 2 June 2025 - Closing date: 4 August 2025 (at 17.00 CEST)
- Second call: January/February 2026 (date tbd)

The deadline for applications will be two months from the launch of each call.

WHERE DOES THE MONEY COME FROM?

The JSA fund is supported by the European Union's Creative Europe Programme.

HOW DOES JSA ENSURE ITS INDEPENDENCE?

All funds provided by donors are managed by a consortium of independent organisations dedicated to the protection of press freedom and independent journalism. No donor is permitted to exert influence over the selection of grantees or their work. Furthermore, JSA is committed to protecting the editorial independence of all grantees. All grants under the JSA grants scheme are awarded by independent juries of experts based on a transparent set of criteria. No representative of any donor or JSA project partner is allowed to sit on or influence any jury.

WHO CAN APPLY?

To be eligible to apply for a JSA grant, applications need to be submitted by a partnership of at least one media outlet (lead) and one research institution (co-lead).

The application should clearly demonstrate the added value of the collaboration and the role of each participating organisation, as well as information about the individual team members (journalists and scientists) who will be directly involved in the implementation of the project and their respective tasks and roles in the proposed investigation.

WHAT IS THE DEFINITION OF A MEDIA OUTLET?

A media outlet refers to a legally registered platform or organisation that distributes news, information, entertainment, or other forms of content to the public. These outlets can include traditional forms of media such as newspapers, television stations, and radio stations, as well as digital platforms like websites and online news services. Media outlets are responsible for producing, curating, and disseminating content to their audience.

WHAT IS THE DEFINITION OF A RESEARCH INSTITUTION?

A research institution is a legally registered public or private organisation dedicated to conducting systematic investigations and studies in order to generate new knowledge, develop technologies, or solve specific problems across various fields of science. These institutions can include universities, government laboratories, independent research centres, or nonprofit organisations.

CAN FREELANCE JOURNALISTS AND/OR SCIENTISTS APPLY?

They can be part of an applying team, but they cannot apply on their own. They need the backup of a media outlet/ research institution.

WHAT ARE THE GEOGRAPHICAL ELIGIBILITY REQUIREMENTS?

In order to be eligible to apply for JSA, partnerships must include at least 1 media outlet and 1 research institution based in a European country that has signed up to the full cross-sectoral strand of the European Union's Creative Europe Programme, which provides core funding for JSA. Eligible countries include all 27 EU member states and the following non-EU countries: Albania,

Bosnia and Herzegovina, Georgia, Iceland, Liechtenstein, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Norway, Serbia and Ukraine.

ARE PARTNERS FROM OTHER COUNTRIES ELIGIBLE TO TAKE PART?

Yes, as long as the lead and co-lead organisations are legally established in European countries that have signed up to the full cross-sectoral strand of the European Union's Creative Europe Programme.

CAN OUR TOPIC BE RELATED TO AN ISSUE OUTSIDE THE EU OR PARTIALLY TAKE PLACE OUTSIDE THE EU?

It is possible to investigate an issue that is also relevant outside the EU, as long as it is directly relevant to European audiences as well. The investigation can (partially) take place outside EU member states and other participating Creative Europe countries.

CAN I SEND IN OUR APPLICATION BY EMAIL?

No. All applications must be submitted through the EJC grant application platform.

CAN I WRITE OUR APPLICATION IN A LANGUAGE OTHER THAN ENGLISH?

No, we only accept applications in English.

DOES ONE MEDIA OUTLET NEED TO APPLY WITH ONE RESEARCH INSTITUTION?

Yes, the team must consist of at least one media outlet and one research institution. It is possible to have more partners.

WHO HAS TO BE IN THE LEAD, THE MEDIA OUTLET OR THE RESEARCH INSTITUTION?

The media outlet has to be in the lead. The application should also identify the leading journalist(s) and a scientist(s) responsible for the implementation.

WHAT INFORMATION IS NECESSARY FOR THE APPLICATION?

Please have a look at the application questions document. It is designed to preview the questions and prepare accordingly. It is not the actual application form.

WHAT COSTS ARE ELIGIBLE FOR FUNDING?

The JSA grant can cover all costs necessary for the project implementation. This can include:

- Staff, salary and human resource costs
- Research-related costs
- Costs for the acquisition or development of technical tools (e.g., software, databases) relevant to investigative journalism
- Travel costs
- Administrative costs, such as communications costs, rent and office costs and accountancy costs
- Translation costs

- Expected legal costs/fees such as for routine pre-publication legal screening

Please note that all costs will be assessed according to need and proportionality. Your budget should be realistic, necessary and reflect the project description.

WHAT EXPENSES ARE NOT COVERED?

The JSA grant cannot cover costs for standard equipment such as computers or video equipment. In general, costs incurred before the signing of the grant agreement are not eligible.

CAN MY PROJECT BE CO-FUNDED BY ANOTHER SOURCE?

Yes. Co-funding, either through self-funding or through another donor is allowed.

WHO RECEIVES THE GRANT AND HOW IS IT DISTRIBUTED WITHIN THE TEAM?

EJC will transfer the grant in instalments to the lead applicant (media outlet)'s bank account in euros. The lead applicant is then responsible for the distribution of funds to the other partners, in accordance with the project application form and the agreed-on budget.

IS IT MANDATORY TO HAVE A BANK ACCOUNT IN ORDER TO RECEIVE THE GRANT?

Yes. The lead applicant needs to have a bank account that can receive international payments from the EU.

The EJC will not be responsible for changes in exchange rates nor for any fees incurred by the lead applicant's banks.

HOW WILL PROJECTS BE EVALUATED?

The evaluation and selection of the projects will be implemented in two stages. In the first stage, JSA will ensure that the proposals comply with the eligibility criteria of the programme. In case there is information missing in the application form or in case the information provided is insufficient to assess the basic eligibility of the proposal, the EJC will reach out to the respective applicant and will require clarifications and additional information.

In the second stage of evaluation, an independent, external jury of 5 members will decide on the winning proposals.

WHICH CRITERIA WILL BE USED TO SELECT THE WINNING PROJECTS?

- Newsworthiness and relevance to the audience (at local/ regional/ national/ transnational level)
- Added value of the collaboration between the media/journalists and research organisation/scientists
- Expected impact of the project
- Team experience and credentials
- Feasibility of the research and publication plan
- Feasibility of the proposed budget (does the tier applied for correspond to the level of complexity of the proposed investigation, activities, team composition, etc.)

HOW LONG DO GRANTEES HAVE TO FINISH THEIR PROJECTS?

After the communication of the winning proposals, grantees will have 8 months to complete their projects and publish their story/ies.

WHAT INFORMATION ABOUT OUR PROJECT IS MADE PUBLIC?

Upon awarding the grants and the signing of grant agreements with the awarded teams, there will be an announcement on the JSA website and other channels of communication. It will include the number of awarded grants, the grant amounts and other general information for the purposes of transparency.

The identity of individual team members and the topics of the projects will be disclosed, unless specifically requested by the teams not to do so. Any public announcements before the end of the investigations will be coordinated with the teams.

I HAVE A QUESTION. WHO SHOULD I CONTACT?

We will organise two online AMA (Ask me Anything) sessions per round.

- Round 1: Monday 16 June 2025 at 11.00 CEST and Monday 7 July 2025 at 11.00 CEST
- Round 2: Dates tbd

If you still have questions, please contact the EJC at jsagrants@ejc.net.

Please note: we will only answer technical questions (e.g. about eligibility or how to apply etc.). We will NOT answer any questions about or assist you with the content of your application!

CAN AN APPLYING TEAM SUBMIT MORE THAN ONE APPLICATION?

Yes. There are no restrictions on the number of applications that may be submitted. The independent jury's decision for the selection of projects will be based entirely on the selection criteria and an attempt to ensure geographical and thematic balance.

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.